

EXAMINING THE iSELF THROUGH THE MODIFIED JOHARI WINDOW

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Part 2

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In this second part of the article, my focus is on the Self in terms of its relationship with others using the Johari Window model – a technique created by two American psychologists, Joseph Luft and Harrington Ingham, from the University of California-Los Angeles in 1955. I have also modified the Johari Window in order to accommodate the iSelf. At the beginning of 2013, my co-principal investigator (Mr Norman Kee) and I did a pilot study using the modified Johari Window of iSelf to examine the cognitive dissonance of iSelf in 12 cyber-gaming addicts. The findings of our study were presented at the Joint 7th SELF Biennial International Conference and Educational Research Association of Singapore Conference. The results suggested that cyber-gaming could cause cognitive dissonance in cyber-gaming addicts but it is not within the scope of this article to delve into that study.

Johari Window on Self

When using the Johari Window, a simple exercise (see Luft, 1969, for detail) can be done where participants are given a list of 56 descriptors (see Chia & Kee, 2013; Luft, 1969) and are asked to pick six that they feel describe their Selves before they involve in any Interact activities, e.g., surfing the Internet, checking emails and playing online games. Peers of the participants are then given the same list, and each is asked to pick six descriptors that describe the participant. **Table 1 on the top of the next page shows the list of the descriptors.**

These descriptors are then mapped onto a grid (see Figure 1), which consists of four quadrants: the Open/Free Area, the Hidden/Facade Area, the Blind Area and the Unknown Area. Each of these quadrants will be described briefly below.

<i>Known to Self</i>	Open/ Free Area	Blind Area	<i>Unknown to Self</i>
<i>Known to Others</i>	Hidden Area	Unknown Area	<i>Unknown to Others</i>

Figure 1. Johari Window Grid

The First Quadrant: The Open/Free Area

The Open/Free Area is that part of Self that an individual can see and others can see, too. The descriptors that are selected by both the individual and his/her peers are placed into this Open/Free Area quadrant. It is this quadrant that represents the individual's traits that both he/she and his/her peers are aware of.

The Second Quadrant: The Hidden Area

The Hidden Area (also known as Facade Area) contains the traits that others can see in the individual but the individual is not aware of. The descriptors in this Hidden Area quadrant are selected only by the individual, but not by any of his/her peers. This quadrant represents the information about the individual that his/her peers are unaware of. It is then up to the individual/peer to disclose this information or not.

The Third Quadrant: The Blind Area

The Blind Area is the most mysterious quadrant in that the individual's unconscious or subconscious Self is not noticed by himself/herself. The descriptors, which the individual did not select, are chosen by his/her peers and are placed into this Blind Area quadrant. It is this quadrant that represents information which the individual is unaware of, but his/her peers are, and they can decide whether and how to inform the individual about his/her "blind spots".

The Fourth Quadrant: The Unknown Area

Finally, the Unknown Area is the individual's uncharted space that he/she does not know of its existence. Even his/her peers do not know, too. The descriptors not selected by the individual or his/her peers are put in this Unknown Area. This quadrant represents the individual's traits that were not known or recognized by anyone participating in the Johari Window activity. One explanation for this is that an individual or his/her peer is not aware at all or because there is collective ignorance of the existence of these traits. One facet of interest in this area concerns our hidden human potential (gifts or talents), i.e., our potential is unknown to us as well as others. This could also be the suppressed Self – probably as a result of post-trauma stress disorder or some

- able
- accepting
- adaptable
- bold
- brave
- calm
- caring
- cheerful
- clever
- complex
- confident
- dependable
- dignified
- energetic
- extroverted
- friendly
- giving
- happy
- helpful
- idealistic
- independent
- ingenious
- intelligent
- introverted
- kind
- knowledgeable
- logical
- loving
- mature
- modest
- nervous
- observant
- organized
- patient
- powerful
- proud
- quiet
- reflective
- relaxed
- religious
- responsive
- searching
- self-assertive
- self-conscious
- sensible
- sentimental
- shy
- silly
- smart
- spontaneous
- sympathetic
- tense
- trustworthy
- warm
- wise
- witty

Table 1. List of Descriptors used in the Johari Window

deep-seated mental/emotional scar not resolved in the past – that might be revealed gradually over a series of hypnotherapy or psychotherapy sessions.

The Modified Johari Window for iSelf

The findings from my pilot study prompted me to modify or redesign the Johari Window in order to accommodate the iSelf (see Figure 2). This is because the iSelf is far more complicated than the physical or physiological Self and its I-Self (nominative Self) and Me-Self (accusative Self). The iSelf involves the Persona and also the Anima (i.e., in the unconscious of the male, it is expressed as a feminine inner personality) or Animus (i.e., in the unconscious of the female, it is expressed as a masculine inner personality). In between Persona and Anima/Animus is a continuum involving External/Public iSelf, Interactive iSelf and Internal/Private iSelf. It also covers another continuum involving the False iSelf, the various Pseudo-iSelves and the True iSelf.

Moreover, between the User (the real Self in this physical world) and the Avatar (the iSelf in the cyber world) there is also another continuum involving Player and Gamer. The difference between Player and Gamer has been discussed in the earlier article *The iSelf (Part 1)*.

As a result, I have to redesign or modify the Johari Window in order to make it more relevant to my application in understanding the inner workings of the iMind of the iSelf in the cyber world (or may I term it as iWorld) (see Figure 2). Using the same Johari Window activity that involves picking six from a list of 56 descriptors (see Table 1) that best describe how an individual User perceives his/her iSelf in the cyber world.

See Figure 2. Modified Johari Window of iSelf on the top of the next column

The First Semicircle: Persona

Persona is defined as the social role or character played by the User (i.e., the physical or physiological Self). It also refers to the mask or appearance that an individual chooses to present himself/herself to the world. Persona is also an

Figure 2. Modified Johari Window of iSelf

external or public iSelf (also the conscious iSelf) known to the User's Self/iSelf as well as others (or Other iSelves). It can be further divided into two quadrants: (1) the Persona as known to iSelf and (2) the Persona as known to Others.

The First Quadrant: Persona known to iSelf

In the first quadrant of Persona known to iSelf, this is the same as the Open/Free Area described earlier, i.e., the iSelf that both the individual and others can see. This quadrant stands for the individual's traits that both he/she and his/her peers are aware of. However, the individual can still put up his/her False Self as a form of personal or social defense to protect the True Self (Winnicott, 1965). The same can be applied and explained of False/True iSelf.

In the cyber world, when other Players'/Gamers' expectations become such an overriding importance, resulting in overlaying or contradicting the original sense of an individual's True iSelf – the one that connects to the very roots of the individual's being – that False iSelf comes into existence. Winnicott (1965) argued that an extreme False Self (or False iSelf in this case) began to develop during

infancy phase as a defense against an unsafe environment or a lack of reasonably attuned care-giving. The same can be explained of a beginner cyber-player/gamer. Through this False iSelf, the Player/Gamer gradually builds up a false set of relationships, and by means of introjections even attains a show of being real or true. Hence, the Player's/Gamer's potential aliveness and creativity has gone unnoticed and his/her iSelf – an empty, barren internal/private iSelf – is concealed behind a mask of independence. However, this Persona of the False iSelf is the ultimate defense against the unthinkable “exploitation of the True Self (True iSelf in this case), which would result in its annihilation” (Jacobus, 2005, p.160).

The Second Quadrant: Persona known to Others

In the second quadrant of Persona known to Others (also known as Other iSelves), this is the same as the Hidden/Facade Area contains the traits of or descriptors selected only by an individual that others can see in his/her iSelf but he/she is not aware of. It represents the information about the individual that others are unaware of. This Persona known to Others helps to expose the Persona of the False iSelf (or the Insecure iSelf), which is already described in the paragraph above.

To understand better how the Persona known to iSelf and the Persona known to Others (Other iSelves) function, let me illustrate using the case of Shin Megami Tensei: Persona – a series of computer games that center around a group of teenagers with the ability to summon facets of their psyches (known as Personae) into being in their battles against the demons. The Persona employs an intricate system of personae to carry out battle commands. These personae represent the multiple pseudo-iSelves an individual can assume or impersonate hiding or protecting the vulnerable True iSelf from the outside physical world or even within the cyber world. For instance, each Player/Gamer has a Persona with its own set of strengths and weaknesses that he/she can summon during a battle against demons. In every battle won, the Player's/Gamer's Persona gains experience points and increases its strength in battle and earning new abilities. Every Player/Gamer has multiple Personae (i.e., multiple pseudo-iSelves), which are alternate iPersonalities (iSelves), laying dormant in the mind of a Player/Gamer with The Potential – a unique ability that remains awake during a nocturnal phenomenon known as the Dark Hour. Other Players/Gamers who are very much engaged in the same series of games will soon notice the hidden traits of other iSelves (unknown to these individuals themselves) over time.

The Second Semicircle: Anima/Animus

Anima and Animus refer to the primary anthropomorphic archetypes of the unconscious mind of an individual's iSelf (be he/she a Player/Gamer). As mentioned earlier, the Anima refers to the expression of a feminine inner person-

ality in the unconscious of the male, while the Animus refers to the expression of a masculine inner personality in the unconscious of the female. It is also an internal or private iSelf (also the unconscious iSelf) that neither the individual nor his/her peers are aware. Anima/Animus can be further divided into two quadrants: (1) the Anima/Animus unknown to iSelf and (2) the Anima/Animus unknown to Others (Other iSelves).

The Third Quadrant: Anima/Animus unknown to iSelf

This third mysterious quadrant is an individual's unconscious or subconscious iSelf, i.e., not being noticed by the individual himself/herself. The quadrant contains those descriptors not selected by the individual but are chosen by his/her peers. This quadrant represents information which the individual is not aware of. However, his/her peers are, and they can decide whether and how to inform the individual about his/her “blind spots”. In cyber-gaming, the individual Player/Gamer will be most vulnerable or open to attack if his/her opponents recognize his/her blind spots that he/she himself/herself is not aware of.

The Fourth Quadrant: Anima/Animus unknown to Others

This fourth quadrant is the individual's uncharted iSelf, which neither he/she nor the others are aware of, that exists in the cyber world. The descriptors not selected by the individual and his/her peers remain in this quadrant, which represents the individual's undiscovered iSelf traits not known by anyone participating in the Johari Window activity. One explanation for this is that the individual or his/her peer is not aware of or because there is collective ignorance of the existence of these iSelf traits. One facet of interest in this area concerns our hidden human potential which is unknown to us as well as others. Often such hidden potentials (e.g., mindfulness) could have tapped on to empower our iSelves for the better in that cyber world.

In this fourth quadrant, the User can take the role of a Player and then move to assume the identity of an individual Avatar as he/she moves about in the cyberspace such as when one is emailing to others or interacting with others in the Facebook. This involves some kind of temporary suspension of disbelief when one “leaves” this physical world and journeys through the cyber world in real-time. Once the Player assumes the Gamer's role, it becomes an immersion of disbelief – a totally different involvement. For instance, in cyber-gaming, the Gamer assumes his/her virtual double Self or look-alike of himself/herself – known as Doppelganger.

In many Massively Multi-player Online Games, Gamers get to choose or design the appearance of their Avatar that moves through the 3D virtual game (Bailenson & Segovia, 2010). There are very few constraints for Avatar creation and with the drag of a slider bar Players can control their identity – height, weight, size, age, gender and even species. The Avatar's iSelf is known to the User, who creates and is

also in control of it. However, according to Bailenson and Segovia (2010), “in many cases, users are not in control of their look-alike avatars; sometimes other gamers or algorithms take control. This is the case when avatars become doppelgangers” (p.176). One good example is the online game World of Warcraft, where Gamers’ Avatars can be mind-controlled by other Gamers. In such a situation, the Gamer has lost all control of his/her Avatar. Now he/she must watch for several seconds or minutes while another Gamer manipulates his/her Avatar – often with intention of sabotage.

Conclusion

The modified Johari Window as a tool serves two purposes: (1) to establish self-awareness and mutual understanding between Users within a cyber-gaming group; and (2) to assess and improve the group’s relationship with other groups.

Today’s computer games offer us a powerful tool in character building or video modeling that we can use to counsel and manage challenging iSelves of our clients through their Doppelgangers. We use computer technology to empower us in engaging clients (particularly, the cyber-gaming addicts) who can relate better to us through that virtual or cyber channel.

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They believe that their wealth almost means somebody else’s poverty. Like it’s a “win-lose” situation. Yet the idea is to become wealthy and through your wealth, to help those around you to also become richer. To raise the level of prosperity not just in your life, but in the lives of others as well. Being extremely wealthy can enable you to be the most altruistic human being on the planet! To truly help others who have not yet attained their vision. To be an example for those less enlightened. To truly change the consciousness of the planet. Powerful words? Yes! Yet think of the love-power that wealth can give you. Having great wealth can be v-e-r-y spiritual.

The Bible is filled with descriptions of spiritual leaders who were very rich. It states, "All things are yours." Let me repeat that. “All things are yours!” “All things!” The word "gold" appears more than four hundred times in the Bible. Know that it is your right to have riches. It’s not about getting a “hand-out”. It’s not about trying to make the Universe give you anything for nothing. It is about opening your unlimited mind to receive the abundance that is your universal right. And it is your right to have wealth. It is your right to have happiness. It is your right to tap into the vast abundant universe.

The mystics had a three-point formula for success: 1) A Clearing or Purification, 2) an Enlightening or Illumination, and 3) a Convergence or Union with the Universe. You can’t add anything new to your house until you make room for it. This is why a mental clearing is crucial.

Most of us know the story of the student who went to a Revered Master for more enlightenment. When he met the master, the student began talking non-stop about everything under the sun. He wanted the master to respect him and realize that he was no dummy; that he was already highly enlightened and knew just about everything about everything. The Master, in his wisdom, listened patiently. Then he asked the student if he’d like a cup of tea. As the tea filled the student’s cup to the brim, the Master simply continued pouring - the excess tea spilling all over the table and the student. The student looked up at the Master in shock, questioning the reason for this unusual display. The Master simply said, “When your cup is so full, there is no room for me to add anything.” The student finally got it. There are many variations of this story and I simply paraphrased one of the versions. As in any profession, hypnotherapists must understand that they’re not going to be able to accept any new ideas about prosperity and abundance until they let go of the old debilitating ones!

To be continued . . .